

Distribution of *Tetragnatha maxillosa* webs in ricefields

P. S. Reddy, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Hyderabad, India; and K. L. Heong, IRRI

Among the spider species that inhabit the rice canopy, orb-weaving spiders (families Araneidae and Tetragnathidae) are often abundant in unsprayed ricefields. *T. maxillosa* is most common.

To learn more about its role in the rice ecosystem, we studied its web distribution and the prey captured in the webs.

T. maxillosa spider webs in an IRRI ricefield transplanted with IR1917 were recorded weekly from 15 d after transplanting (DT), at nine sampling points during the 1988 dry season (DS) and 12 sampling points during the 1989 wet season (WS). Vertical web distribution was measured from the hub of the web to the ground.

Evidence of predation by *T. maxillosa* was obtained by removing all prey carcasses in each web, then counting new prey caught. All arthropods found dead

Prey spectrum caught by *T. maxillosa* in ricefields. IRRI, 1988 DS and 1989 WS.

Prey	Prey caught		Total prey from an order (%)
	no.	%	
DIPTERA			
Tipulidae	4	2.2	55.9
Anthomyidae	1	0.5	
Muscidae	62	33.3	
Culicidae	24	12.9	
<i>Criptochironomus</i> sp.	2	1.1	
<i>Nillobezzia</i> sp.	1	0.5	
Drosophilidae	6	3.2	
<i>Megaselia scalaris</i>	1	0.5	
<i>Chironomus</i> sp.	3	1.6	
HEMIPTERA			
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	2	1.1	
HOMOPTERA			
<i>Nephotettix</i> sp.	18	9.1	21.0
<i>R. dorsalis</i>	3	1.6	
<i>N. lugens</i>	11	5.9	
<i>S. furcifera</i>	5	2.7	
EPHEMEROPTERA			
	15	8.1	8.1
LEPIDOPTERA			
<i>S. incertulas</i>	6	3.2	14.0
<i>C. medinalis</i>	16	8.6	
<i>N. aenescens</i>	2	1.1	
<i>R. atimeta</i>	2	1.1	
ARANEAE			
<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	2	1.1	1.1
Total	186		

Vertical distribution of *T. maxillosa* webs in IR1917 canopies at IRRI.

in a web were considered prey. Prey were collected and preserved in 70% ethyl alcohol for laboratory examination.

The crop canopy was divided equally into top, middle, and bottom portions. Ninety-six percent of the webs found were built in the top and middle portions (see figure). Prey caught were primarily insects (98.9%) (see table). Dipterans,

mostly scavengers, made up 56%; 34.9% were other rice pests.

Although *T. maxillosa* is often abundant in the rice ecosystem, its role as a rice pest predator appears negligible. With relatively weak webs constructed in the top and middle portions of the canopy, its main prey seems to be weak fliers. □